

Livelihood Analysis of Rice Processors in Kwara State

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Abstract

Rice is a staple food in Nigeria, yet the role of processing in shaping household welfare remains less documented compared to production. This study assessed rice processors in Kwara State with emphasis on levels of participation, profitability, and the determinants of involvement. Primary data were obtained from 150 respondents and analyzed using descriptive statistics, gross margin analysis, ordered logistic regression, correlation, and regression techniques. Findings revealed that hulling accounted for the highest participation (94%), while polishing and parboiling emerged as the most profitable stages, yielding gross margins of ₦1,884.86 and ₦1,513.73 respectively. The ordered logistic regression model was statistically significant, indicating that gender, age, household size, and satisfaction were major determinants of involvement. A positive correlation ($r = 0.3713$) was observed between level of involvement and livelihood status. Regression results further showed that household income, years of experience, and intensity of processing significantly improved livelihood outcomes, with an R^2 value of 0.4366 explaining 43.66% of variation. Overall, 58.67% of processors recorded high livelihood status, while 41.33% remained in the low category. The study concludes that modernization, improved financing, and stronger infrastructure are essential for enhancing the welfare contributions of rice processing in Kwara State.

1.0 Introduction

Poverty remains one of the most pressing development challenges globally, with more than 80 percent of the world's extremely poor people relying primarily on agriculture for survival (World Bank, 2025). Beyond income and consumption, poverty also reflects deprivations in education, health, living standards, and access to basic infrastructure, with rural dwellers being the most vulnerable (Qadir et al., 2023; Sanusi, 2024).

Rice is a major staple in Nigeria, yet domestic production continues to fall short of demand, sustaining dependence on imports (Ekundayo, 2023). Policy reforms such as the Rice Transformation Agenda and import-substitution measures have reduced import bills and stimulated production. Recent studies show that bottlenecks in domestic processing: high post-harvest losses, low equipment effectiveness in de-

husking and milling, limited capital, and unreliable energy supply, prevent production gains from translating into stronger food security and rural development. Strengthening the processing segment through modernization, maintenance, training, financing, improved storage, and reliable energy could reduce losses, increase value retention locally, raise both processor and farmer incomes, and amplify the structural-development effects of national rice policies (Jaafar et al., 2023; Achebe et al., 2024). Rice processing encompasses pre-processing: impurity removal, screening, drying; primary processing: husking, milling, polishing; and final processing: packaging and storage. In Nigeria, these activities are still dominated by small-scale operators using traditional technologies. Reliance on manual methods produces substandard rice, limits market access, reduces farm-gate prices, and curtails livelihood benefits for processors (Obisesan et al., 2024). Technologies have evolved to improve each stage, including impurity removal with de-stoning machines, de-husking and polishing machinery, enhanced sorting, and control-line equipment (Adetola & Akindahunsi, 2020; Olayanju et al., 2024). By adopting systematic approaches from pre-processing to final processing, rice can be transformed into a market-ready product with improved quality and shelf life (Banjo et al., 2025).

Federal and State Government initiatives promote the consumption of locally produced rice, but these goals are constrained by weak processing and limited marketing channels (Iweka et al., 2022). The reviewed literature underscores persistent gaps in understanding how processing practices, technological adoption, and market access shape the livelihood outcomes of processors. Research on rice entrepreneurial activities highlights the financial and welfare implications of processing, especially when comparing returns across processing levels (Hussaini et al., 2021). Studies examining efficiency differentials in processing techniques show that technological advancement: traditional methods, hybrid systems, semi-mechanized equipment, and fully modern technologies, directly affect product quality, profitability, and livelihood outcomes (Obianefo et al., 2023). Furthermore, assessments of local processing practices in Southwestern Nigeria reveal that inadequate packaging, poor drying, weak storage, and inefficient distribution undermine quality and shelf life, with direct implications for processors' economic resilience (Banjo et al., 2025).

Despite increasing attention to rice value chains in Nigeria, little is known about how rice processing influences livelihoods in Kwara State, particularly in terms of income, processing typologies, and participation drivers. This study addresses this gap by examining the livelihood contributions of rice processors in Kwara State, thereby advancing understanding of their role in rural development and poverty reduction.

2.0 Literature Review

The purpose of this research is to analyze the livelihood status of rice processors in Kwara State, Nigeria. While considerable attention has been devoted to rice production and value chain development in Africa, limited evidence exists on the livelihood contributions of rice processing, particularly in Nigeria's North-Central region. This study therefore evaluates income levels, livelihood outcomes, and the

factors influencing involvement in rice processing, with the aim of addressing a critical gap in agricultural livelihood research.

Agriculture remains the primary driver of growth in Africa, yet most farmers in Nigeria still operate at subsistence or small-scale levels (Gabriel et al., 2023). These farms are characterized by low-skilled labor and reliance on family units, which contribute to persistent yield gaps. Productivity is further constrained by challenges such as soil infertility, limited access to modern technology, poor market linkages, and weak financing systems (Akinbode et al., 2024). Within this context, rice has emerged as one of the most widely consumed staples in Nigeria, cutting across both rural and urban populations (Akpan et al., 2024; Simpa et al., 2024).

Despite significant production increases in recent years, the demand for rice continues to outpace local supply, leading to high levels of importation (Familusi & Oranu, 2020). To address this, strategies such as the National Rice Development Strategy (NRDS) were launched in Nigeria, with ambitious targets to boost local production and reduce imports (Siéwé et al., 2023; Edwards et al., 2023). In Nigeria, rice has become central to agricultural transformation programmes. The Agricultural Transformation Agenda (ATA) and subsequent policies significantly expanded production, with domestic output rising steadily in the last decade (Abah et al., 2021). Regional frameworks like the ECOWAS Agricultural Policy (ECOWAP) also reinforced this drive toward self-sufficiency (Nwozor & Olanrewaju, 2020). Scholars propose different pathways to food security: large-scale mechanized production to close the demand–supply gap (Edefe et al., 2023), or smallholder support through input provision and market access (Akinwale et al., 2023). Rice’s importance in Nigerian diets underscores the urgency of a balanced approach, with attention directed toward post-harvest handling and processing. Traditional labor-intensive practices continue to reduce the quality and competitiveness of local rice (Ibrahim et al., 2023), whereas adoption of modern processing technologies improves milling quality and increases market value (Jaafar et al., 2023). Additionally, rice by-products such as husks and bran are increasingly recognized for their value in animal feed, renewable energy, food additives, and other uses (Igbo et al., 2023).

Although rice production has received considerable research attention, rice processing as a livelihood activity remains relatively underexplored in Nigeria. Studies such as Sadiq et al. (2024) show that rice processing enterprises among microfinance beneficiaries in Jigawa State are both viable and profitable, generating additional income and employment opportunities. Similarly, Obianefo et al. (2023) report that small-scale processors in Anambra State face persistent technology and infrastructure gaps, which reduce efficiency and constrain livelihood outcomes. Value chain studies further highlight that value addition enhances the welfare of actors, particularly small-scale processors and traders (Adi et al., 2024). Achebe et al. (2023) also observe that many small-scale processors in Nigeria’s de-husking lines operate with low equipment effectiveness and frequent downtime, which lowers process capacity. These findings point to the need for better equipment, stronger market linkages, and improved operational capacity to maximize livelihood benefits.

In Kwara State specifically, limited studies have examined how rice processors’ activities translate into livelihood outcomes, creating a gap that this study addresses.

This review underscores the central role of rice in Nigeria's agricultural and food systems, as well as the policy, technological, and institutional efforts directed toward strengthening its value chain. Significant advances have been recorded in research on rice cultivation, marketing, storage, and value addition, yet the livelihood implications of rice processing remain underexplored in Kwara State. Studies demonstrate that modern processing technologies, entrepreneurship, cooperative participation, and value chain integration contribute to incomes and food security, but limited evidence exists on their direct effects on processors' welfare. To address this gap, the present study employs the Sustainable Livelihood Framework to analyze income levels, determinants of participation, and livelihood outcomes among rice processors in Kwara State.

3.0 Materials and Methods

The study was conducted in Kwara State, located in the North-Central region of Nigeria, with Ilorin as the state capital. Kwara State was created on 27th May, 1967, and lies between latitudes 8°30' and 8°50' N and longitudes 4°20' and 4°35' E. It covers a total land area of approximately 36,825 km². The state shares boundaries with the Republic of Benin to the west, Niger State to the north, Kogi State to the east, and Ekiti, Osun, and Oyo States to the south.

According to the 2006 National Population Census, the state has a population of about 2,365,353 people, comprising mainly Yoruba, Nupe, and Bariba ethnic groups, with minority Fulani settlements. The inhabitants engage in diverse economic activities, particularly trading and farming. Major crops cultivated in the state include rice, yam, cassava, cocoyam, guinea corn, citrus, and vegetables. Administratively, Kwara State is divided into 16 Local Government Areas (LGAs), grouped into four agricultural zones under the Kwara State Agricultural Development Project (Kwara ADP, 2019).

Source of Data

The study relied on primary data, which were collected through the administration of structured questionnaires and interview schedules. The instruments were designed to obtain detailed information from rice processors on socio-economic characteristics, processing activities, and livelihood outcomes.

Sampling Technique

The study population consisted of rice processors in Kwara State. A three-stage sampling procedure was adopted. In the first stage, Patigi and Edu Local Government Areas were purposively selected owing to their prominence in rice production and processing. In the second stage, five communities were randomly chosen from each of the two LGAs. At the third stage, 15 rice processors were randomly selected from each of the sampled communities, giving a total of 150 respondents.

Analytical Techniques

Data collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics, Gross-margin analysis, Ordered Logistic Regression Analysis, and Correlation and Regression Analysis analytical frameworks is briefly discussed below.

Descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage and mean were used to analyze the socioeconomic characteristics of the rice processor and their level of involvement in the level of rice processing

Gross Margin Analysis was applied to compare the costs and returns of male and female rice processors in the study area. It measures the share of total sales revenue that remains after deducting the variable costs of production. A higher gross margin implies greater financial flexibility, since more revenue is available to meet other expenses and obligations. This analytical tool is widely used in evaluating profitability in agricultural enterprises. For example, Olumayowa et al. (2024) employed gross margin, alongside profitability index and rate of return measures, to assess the performance of local rice processing enterprises in Nigeria.

The Gross Margin is expressed as

$$GM = TR - TVC$$

Where, GM = Gross Margin

TR = Total Revenue

TVC = Total Variable Cost

Ordered Logistic Regression Analysis was used to examine the factors influencing involvement in rice processing. This technique is appropriate when the dependent variable is categorical and ordered, as in the case of levels of participation. It has been applied in several agribusiness studies to understand how socio-economic characteristics shape participation and livelihood outcomes. For instance, (Ajibade et al., 2024) applied ordered regression in their assessment of rice processing enterprises in Ibaji, Kogi State.

The model for this study is specified as:

$$Y_i = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \dots + \beta_n X_n + U$$

Where Y_i (Dependent Variable) = Level of Involvement; Male=0, Female=1

X_1 to X_n = Independent Variables

X_1 = Sex (Female 1, Male 0)

X_2 = Age

X_3 = Household size

X_4 = Household Income

X_5 = Processing experience

X_6 = Employment

X_7 = Satisfaction

α = Intercept

β = Coefficients

U_i = Error Term

Correlation and regression was used to examine the contribution of the level of processing to livelihood status.

The equation is given thus

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$$Y_i = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \dots + \beta_n X_n + U$$

Where Y= Livelihood status

X_i to X_n =Independent Variables

X₁= Level of involvement

X₂= Gender (Female 1, Male 0)

X₃= Age

X₄ = Household size

X₅ = Household Income

X₆ = Years of experience

X₇ = Education

X₈ = Marital Status

X₈ = Satisfaction (with overall infrastructure)

X₉ = Employment

α =Intercept

β =Coefficients

U_i =Error Term

4.0 Result and Discussion

Distribution of Respondents by Stage of Rice Processing

Stages of Rice processing	Frequency	Percentage
Parboiling (partially cooking paddy)	77	51.33
Hulling (removing husk)	141	94
Polishing	76	50.67
Sorting and grading	42	28
Destoning	7	4.67
Other (Please specify)	1	0.67

The table reveals differing levels of participation across rice processing stages in the study area. Hulling recorded the highest involvement at 94%, followed by parboiling (51.33%) and polishing (50.67%). Sorting and grading accounted for 28%, while destoning had the least participation at 4.67%. Only 0.67% of respondents engaged in other unspecified activities, indicating that most processors concentrated on the major recognized stages of rice processing.

Cost Structure, Revenue, and Profitability Ranking of Rice Processing Activities

Processing Activities	Paddy Rice	Labour Cost	Energy Cost	Maintenance Cost	Total Cost	Total Revenue	Gross Margin	Ranking
Parboiling	778.9	6.08	4.40	4.97	794.35	2308.08	1513.73	2 nd
Hulling	778.9	6.50	4.81	4.71	794.92	2100	1305.08	4 th
Polishing	778.9	16.22	4.33	4.82	804.27	2689.13	1884.86	1 st
Sorting and grading	778.9	5.16	4.95	4.93	793.93	2105.22	1311.29	3 rd
Destoning	778.9	13.54	14.00	15.83	822.27	1530.77	708.50	5 th

The analysis of paddy rice processing activities reveals clear differences in costs, revenues, and profitability across the various stages. Polishing emerged as the most profitable stage, generating the highest gross margin of ₦1,884.86 and ranking 1st, despite its relatively higher labour cost. Parboiling followed with a gross margin of ₦1,513.73, placing it 2nd, while sorting and grading ranked 3rd with ₦1,311.29. Hulling was slightly lower, with a gross margin of ₦1,305.08, ranking 4th. Destoning recorded the least profitability, producing a gross margin of ₦708.50 and ranking 5th, largely due to its higher labour, energy, and maintenance costs. Overall, the results show that profitability varies widely across processing activities, with polishing and parboiling standing out as the most financially rewarding stages.

Ordered Logistic Regression Results on Determinants of Participation in Rice Processing

Participation level	Coef.	Std. Err.	Z	P>z
Gender (Female =1, Male =0)	1.123326	.5011491	2.24	0.025
Age	.0988474	.0308719	3.20	0.001
Household size	-.3867369	.1090741	-3.55	0.000
Household income	.0000194	.0000122	1.60	0.110
Years of experience	-.0031762	.0325234	-0.10	0.922

Education	-.1558246	.2085012	-0.75	0.455
Employment	.2788023	.1690401	1.65	0.099
Satisfaction (with overall infrastructure such as road and so on)	.608809	.1780265	3.42	0.001
/cut1	4.503567	1.508624		
/cut2	4.861452	1.519098		
/cut3	6.101381	1.567726		
/cut4	8.346889	1.643143		

Pseudo R² = 0.1187
 Prob > chi² = 0.0000
 LR chi²(8) = 46.46

The ordered logistic regression results indicate that the model is statistically significant (LR chi², p < 0.001) with a Pseudo R² of 0.1187, showing that the predictors explain about 11.87% of the variation in levels of involvement. Gender is a significant determinant, as female respondents were more likely to participate in rice processing than their male counterparts ($\beta = 1.123$, p = 0.025). Age also had a positive and significant effect ($\beta = 0.0988$, p = 0.001), suggesting that involvement increases with experience and maturity. Household size, however, negatively influenced participation ($\beta = -0.3867$, p < 0.001), implying that larger households may limit the extent of individual engagement in processing activities, possibly due to competing domestic responsibilities or resource constraints. In addition, satisfaction with current circumstances exerted a strong positive effect ($\beta = 0.6088$, p = 0.001), indicating that respondents who reported higher levels of wellbeing were more likely to be actively engaged in rice processing. These findings are consistent with those of similar research in Nasarawa State, where household size, income, and processing experience were also found to significantly influence participation in rice processing (Yusuf et al., 2025).

Distribution of Rice Processors by Livelihood and Welfare Indicators

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
average monthly income from rice		
≤25,000	77	51.33
26000 – 50000	56	37.33

≥51000		11.33
	17	
access to additional sources of income		
Yes	46	30.67
No	104	69.33
expenditure on food		
≤15,000	46	30.67
16000 – 30000	81	54.00
≥31000	23	15.33
ability to cover the household's food needs		
Always	2	1.33
Sometimes	121	80.67
Rarely	19	12.67
Never	8	5.33
experienced difficulty in access enough food		
Yes	123	82.00
No	27	18.00
consume your own processed rice		
Yes	142	94.67
No	8	5.33
availability of a reliable source of food		
strongly agree	17	11.33
Agree	94	62.67
Disagree	38	25.33
strongly disagree	1	0.67

Improved standard of living

improved slightly	99	66.00
no change	51	34.00

expenses on utility

≤2500	55	36.67
2600 – 5000	31	20.67
5100 -7500	45	30.00
≥7600	19	12.67

shelter ownership

Own	119	79.33
Rent	31	20.67

the primary mode of transportation

Car	16	10.67
Motorcycle	127	84.67
Bicycle	7	4.67

access to healthcare

Yes	130	86.67
No	20	13.33

Savings

Yes	85	56.67
No	65	43.33

Investment

Yes	61	40.67
No	89	59.33

The assessment of livelihood status among rice processors indicates modest but differentiated outcomes. A majority (51.33%) earn ₦25,000 or less per month from processing activities, while 37.33% fall within the ₦26,000–₦50,000 range. Only 11.33% record earnings of ₦51,000 and above, reflecting limited high-income opportunities. Although 30.67% have additional sources of income, most respondents (69.33%) rely exclusively on rice processing, thereby exposing them to greater

economic vulnerability. Despite relatively low earnings, 56.67% of processors reported some level of savings, and 40.67% engage in investments, suggesting modest financial resilience. Food expenditure remains substantial, with 54% of households spending between ₦16,000 and ₦30,000 monthly. However, food security remains a challenge: only 1.33% always meet their food needs, 80.67% sometimes achieve sufficiency, while 18% rarely or never do. This observation resonates with findings among rice processors in Jigawa State, where significant welfare inequality and widespread food insecurity were also reported (Sanusi and Sani, 2024).

Distribution of Respondents by Livelihood Index

Livelihood index	Frequency	Percentage
Low (≤ 0.5)	62	41.33
High (> 0.5)	88	58.67
	150	100

The distribution of the Livelihood Index indicates that 58.67% of rice processors fall within the high category (> 0.5), reflecting relatively favorable economic conditions for the majority. Conversely, 41.33% are classified in the low category (≤ 0.5), underscoring persistent challenges to economic stability and security among a substantial share of the population.

Correlation Between Livelihood Status and Level of Involvement in Rice Processing

	Livelihood status	Involvement
Livelihood status	1.0000	0.3713
Level of involvement	0.3713	1.0000

The correlation coefficient between livelihood status and level of involvement is 0.3713. This positive correlation suggests that as the level of involvement in a livelihood activity increases, the livelihood status tends to improve. Therefore, as the level of involvement in different rice processing activities, such as hulling, parboiling, polishing, sorting and grading, fortification, etc. increases, livelihood status also tends to improve by approximately 0.3713 units.

Regression analysis showing the effect of level of involvement on livelihood

Livelihood status	Coef.	Std. Err.	T	P>t
Level of involvement	.5097451	.1363258	3.74	0.000***

Household size	-.092535	.2656125	-0.35	0.728
Household income	.7912327	.1667646	4.74	0.000***
Years of experience	.6311878	.1821218	3.47	0.001***
Education level	.2518457	.1987126	1.27	0.207
Gender	-.9357028	.5226007	-1.79	0.076
Age	.0301242	.031982	0.94	0.348
Satisfaction (with overall infrastructure)	-.1200635	.1761919	-0.68	0.497
Marital status	-.1202843	.2657567	-0.45	0.652
_cons	10.75534	1.377545	7.81	0.000

R-square =0.4366

*** significant at 1%

The estimation results of this study reveal that the level of involvement in rice processing ($\beta = 0.5097$, $p < 0.001$), household income ($\beta = 0.7912$, $p < 0.001$), and years of experience ($\beta = 0.6312$, $p = 0.001$) exert significant positive effects on livelihood status, jointly explaining 43.66% of the observed variation ($R^2 = 0.4366$). These results are consistent with the findings of Mahmud et al. (2024), who report that higher processing intensity among rice processors in Patigi LGA is closely associated with greater profitability and improved welfare outcomes. Their evidence supports the view that deeper engagement in processing activities strengthens income generation and enhances livelihood security. In a related contribution, Ojo et al. (2024) demonstrate that diversification of income sources significantly reduces poverty and improves welfare among rural households in Kwara State. Their results highlight the critical role of household income in shaping livelihood outcomes, giving strong geographic relevance to the present study's findings.

5.0 Conclusion

Rice processing plays a vital role in enhancing rural livelihoods in Kwara State, generating income, employment, and modest financial resilience for households. The study shows that higher levels of involvement, household income, and years of experience significantly improve livelihood outcomes, with a majority of processors achieving high livelihood status. While profitability varies across processing stages, activities such as hulling, polishing, and parboiling provide strong economic

contributions. Strengthening access to modern processing technologies, affordable credit, and targeted capacity-building will further enhance income opportunities, promote economic stability, and reinforce the role of rice processing in poverty reduction and rural development.

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